

EFFECT OF ARTIFICIAL CORROSION ON RETARDATION OF FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH – ASSESSMENT BY LOCAL CYCLIC PLASTICITY –

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In recent years, several numerical research projects have focused on fatigue crack closure. This study presents numerical investigations concerning the retardation of fatigue crack growth induced by artificial corrosion products on crack surfaces. To conduct these analyses, the authors employed an unconventional elasto-plasticity material model they developed. Consequently, the evaluation of fatigue crack growth life was predicated on the cyclic elasto-plastic response at the crack tip. The simulation of the volume expansion caused by corrosion was accomplished by applying heat input to the crack surface elements. The results indicate the occurrence of fatigue crack closure, leading to a subsequent reduction in stress and strain ranges at the crack tip. Furthermore, the obtained $a - N$ results exhibit good accuracy, not only in predicting significant crack extension but also in modelling the subsequent recovery behaviour, aligning closely with experimental findings.

Keywords: Fatigue crack propagation, Crack closure, Corrosion, Elasto-plastic analysis

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring the integrity of steel structures against fatigue-related issues is extremely important in engineering structures both in the present and for the foreseeable future. Therefore, the development of accessible maintenance techniques and precise numerical methodologies for assessing their efficacy is of critical importance. In particular, the utilisation of the crack closure technique emerges as a cost-effective approach for this purpose.

One of the most practical methods is to take advantage of foreign objects to trigger off crack closure and retard the crack growth rate (hereafter, da/dN) by increasing the stress intensity factor at the crack opening ΔK_{op} and subsequently reducing the effective stress intensity factor range ΔK_{eff} .

Takahashi et al. [1-2] reported da/dN resulting from the injection of alumina and magnetic particle paste into fatigue cracks. Their investigation analysed the influence of various factors such as the nature of the inserted objects, particle size, and hardness on the retardation of crack growth.

Putri et al. [3] conducted experimental work interested in fatigue life extensions by injecting 65% HNO₃ liquid, chosen for its ease of application due to its pumpability and capillarity characteristics. Consequently, fatigue lives were retarded due to the volume of generated corrosion products under

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different conditions in terms of crack lengths and loading values. Additional experimental studies have been published, focusing on materials such as epoxy resin with alumina powder [4], plating metals [5], artificial steel asperities [6], and others.

However, these experiments were conducted under limited conditions with regard to quantitatively assessing parameters such as the quantity of inserted product, crack length, and loading values. Moreover, the application of numerical analyses has not been considered in these investigations.

On the other hand, the authors [7-8] developed the unconventional plasticity model (Fatigue SS model, FSS hereafter), capable of accounting for the smooth development of plastic strain even for stress states below the macroscopic yield stress satisfying the loading criterion. This aspect is of fundamental importance since conventional plasticity theories cannot catch the progressive inelastic stretch accumulation nor the progressive opening of the hysteresis loops for loading conditions generating stress states within the elastic domain. On the other hand, the FSS model is able to catch a realistic material description in low and high cycles loading conditions, as proved in previous works of the authors [9-14]. More recently, the aforementioned numerical model has been used to formulate a methodology for the investigation of the crack propagation phenomenon [15-17]. This approach holds promise for gaining deeper insights into issues governed by plasticity, such as crack closure and crack face contact.

In this research, numerical investigations were conducted with the aim of replicating the observed retardation in fatigue life resulting from the presence of artificial corrosion products, as previously investigated by Putri et al [3].

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

This section describes the abstract of the experimental work conducted by Putri et al. [3].

The CT specimens, made from the rolled structural steel SS400, were adopted for the fatigue experiments in order to investigate the crack growth behaviour and the wedge effect due to corrosion products.

FIGURE 1 Procedures of corrosion fatigue test

TABLE 1 Test matrix

Case	Load (kN)	Load ratio, R	Crack length at injection (mm)
SP-1	12.5 (13.0-0.5)	0.038	40.3
SP-2	10.0 (10.5-0.5)	0.048	39.8
SP-3	10.0 (10.5-0.5)	0.048	29.4
SP-4	7.5 (8.0-0.5)	0.063	38.9
SP-5	7.5 (9.375-1.875)	0.2	29.9

FIGURE 1 illustrates the procedures of the experimental investigation. Firstly, a fatigue crack propagation test is performed in air to get a certain length of the crack, a_{co} . Then, a corrosion accelerator, 65% HNO_3 liquid, is injected into the crack faces under the lower test frequency. Finally, the fatigue test in air is resumed after 24 hours of the curing period. Five different conditions were examined, considering different values of the crack length when the injection is performed and different loading conditions as reported in TABLE 1.

FIGURE 5 and FIGURE 6 report the test results for the specimen SP-3 in TABLE 1, since this particular sample displays the significant changes in crack growth behaviour before and after corrosion.

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION

Analysis conditions

The specimen under investigation, shown in FIGURE 2 is a compact tension specimen (CT specimen) with a thickness of 6mm. The half part of the tested specimen was modelled with hexahedral elements to reduce the computational cost. The model consists of a total of 42,696 hexahedral elements (i.e., HEX8) and 53,172 nodes. The minimum element size is 50 μ m, located in the vicinity of the crack path. Additionally, the element widths taper progressively towards the symmetrical plane to replicate a plane strain condition.

A fatigue crack was initiated from the bottom of the notch part and propagated perpendicular to the loading direction. Crack propagation was numerically simulated by changing two types of contact regions (small sliding for crack faces and tying for the futural crack region). Boundary conditions were set to reproduce the symmetrical nature of the specimen and correspond to the testing conditions. The numerical analyses were conducted by employing a user subroutine for the commercial code ADVENTURECluster2022, implementing the Fatigue SS model constitutive equations [7-8]. Cyclic loading is applied on the upper side of the CT sample for a total of ten cycles, as nodal forces under constant load amplitude. The condition of the SP-3 in TABLE 1 is simulated in this paper.

For the quantification of crack growth rate da/dN , the authors proposed the following Equation (1).

FIGURE 2 FE model and boundary conditions

$$da/dN = \Delta a/N_c \quad (1)$$

Where Δa is a material parameter, or eventually a function that has crack growth length as a factor, which depends on the steel type and element size in the vicinity of the crack.

In the case of the crack growth retardation by corrosion products, it is strongly suggested by the author's work that crack growth retardation is caused by the accumulated volume of corrosion products on crack surfaces [18]. In other words, the corrosion products promote the crack surface contact (crack closure) and subsequent decrease of the strain range $\Delta \epsilon_t$ at the crack tip. Therefore, an internal heat generation term denoted as Q was introduced in the simulation analysis aimed at capturing the crack surface expansion and closure by corrosion products. This term was identified to exhibit a correlation with both the temporary reduction in da/dN and the subsequent recovery behaviour after corrosion. Q was input to crack face elements characterised by orthotropic material properties.

Subsequently, the material parameters on crack face elements were reverted to match those of the other regions governed by the FSS model. Lastly, cyclic elasto-plastic analyses were conducted to assess the development of irreversible deformations and to judge the progressive opening of the crack. The plastic history between subsequent cracks opening was considered in the numerical simulations.

For comprehensive details on the FSS model, readers are directed to reference [7-8], and for a thorough understanding of the analysis procedures, reference [17] is recommended.

Results and discussion

FIGURE 3 illustrates the stress distribution around the crack along the loading direction at the final elasto-plastic cycle. Firstly, it is possible to observe that the element expansion due to heat generation Q results a significant reduction in the distance between the crack faces. Thus, the faces can easily

FIGURE 3 Stress distributions (in y direction) at the final elasto-plastic cycle before and after simulation analysis for corrosion (Magnification of 5X)

TABLE 2 Stress intensity factors K_{max} , K_{min} and ΔK_{eff}

Case	K_{max} [MPa · $\sqrt{m}$]	K_{min} [MPa · $\sqrt{m}$]	ΔK_{eff} [MPa · $\sqrt{m}$]
Before expansion	15.31	0.73	14.58
After expansion	15.31	12.98	2.33

come into contact with each other under cyclic loading. In terms of the stress distribution, an increase in stress is observed under minimum loading conditions around the crack, while negligible stress differences are visible under maximum loading conditions. This implies that the expansion of the crack faces induces crack closure and maintains elevated stress values, even under the minimum loading. This phenomenon aligns with findings obtained from strain gauge measurements conducted in the vicinity of the crack tip, as reported in reference [3] and the author's work [18].

Stress intensity factors K_{max} , K_{min} and ΔK_{eff} are shown in TABLE 2. They are evaluated by the theoretical equation of ASTM [19] and the unloading elastic compliance method [20]. As can be seen in the table, the element expansion contributes to the significant reduction in ΔK_{eff} .

FIGURE 4 represents stress-strain responses along the loading direction at the crack tip nodes on the symmetrical plane. Black, red, and blue lines represent the data before, during, and after the

FIGURE 4 Stress-strain curves at the crack tip node, for test case SP-3, with a fatigue load range of 10.0 kN (10.5 kN - 0.5 kN)

simulation analyses of corrosion, respectively. This graph shows significant decrease in the total strain range $\Delta\varepsilon_t$ and increase in mean stress σ_m , which reflect the distributions in FIGURE 3.

To predict the da/dN , the identification of a single Δa value is needed, as per Equation (1). In this research, Δa was selected to correspond with a specific da/dN data value at the crack length of $a=26\text{mm}$. In other words, a numerical analysis is implemented to obtain crack initiation life N_c at the crack length of 26mm. Subsequently, Δa was determined by comparing it with experimental data for da/dN and N_c .

FIGURE 5 shows the numerical $a - da/dN$ results and the experimental ones marked as $\oplus$. Firstly, in the region before corrosion, the overall trends are consistent, thus confirming the validity of the crack propagation method developed by the authors [17]. Notably, despite the use of just one set of values for Δa and Q , the pronounced reduction in da/dN at the crack length affected by corrosion and the subsequent recovery trend are well reproduced.

Finally, FIGURE 6 displays the $a - N$ relationship derived by integrating the trend in FIGURE 5. The number of cycles, represented on the longitudinal axis, is computed through the integration of the $a - da/dN$ relationship. Overall, this graph shows good agreement with the experimental results. According to Equation (1), the denominator N_c should assume high values in order to follow the trend $da/dN = \Delta a/N_c$, since the Δa is assigned as a unique value in this series of analyses. In addition, according to the standard for N_c [21], crack initiation life N_c is very sensitive to total strain range $\Delta\varepsilon_t$ in the high cycle region. Therefore, appropriate standards for fatigue life evaluation appears to be crucial for the correct assessment of the phenomenon and they should be established depending on a series of factors such as steel type, thermal history, etc.

In this study, the crack face elements contribute to crack closure, and they adopt the same material properties as in the base metal. A different description would be required under the compressive state, which allows the large deformation by corrosion products. The incorporation of actual material properties of corrosion products remains a subject for future investigations and research works.

FIGURE 5 $a - da/dN$ relationships: Experiment vs. Analysis (HNO_3 injection at $a = 29.4$ mm)

FIGURE 6 $a - N$ relationships: Experiment vs. Analysis (HNO_3 injection at $a = 29.4$ mm)

CONCLUSION

The paper conducted an investigation into the viability of an evaluation method designed to track crack retardation induced by corrosion products, utilising heat generation (Q) within an elasto-plastic framework, employing the FSS model. Numerical analyses were applied with only one set of Δa and internal heat generation Q parameters. The main aspects of the present work can be summarised as follows:

1. Numerical analyses were carried out to follow the crack growth retardation due to the presence of corrosion products. In detail, the work introduced a heat generation procedure for the crack face elements with orthotropic material properties within the framework of an evaluation method previously developed by the authors. The results confirmed a significant increase in stress under minimum loading around the crack, which accounts for the reduction of ΔK_{eff} .
2. Stress-strain curves, derived from data collected at the crack tip node, indicated a reduction in total strain $\Delta \varepsilon_t$ before and after the simulation analyses for corrosion.
3. Through a comparative analysis involving experimental and numerical investigations, a single set of data for the Δa and the internal heat generation Q parameters sufficed for a reliable numerical simulation of the phenomenon. In fact, the overall numerical trend shows good agreement with experimental crack growth behaviour, not only in the temporary retardation of the crack propagation but also in the recovery da/dN slope. This congruence was similarly observed in the $a - N$ relationship.

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